

RES-Q: Self-evolving Post-disaster Response Plans Utilizing Semantics

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ABSTRACT

During the last decade, communities at local and national level are implementing actions geared towards improving disaster resilience. In this context, the importance of ICT in disaster risk management is rapidly increasing globally, especially nowadays amidst the climate crisis and the covid-19 pandemic. However, disaster risk management operations require contributions and collaboration of different type of actors and infrastructures with different functions, rules, protocols and datasets, forming complex contexts in decision making and event coordination. Hence, semantic interoperability between the various stakeholders is one of the challenges to be confronted. In this paper, we present the RES-Q (RESCUE) approach that proposes an information technology solution concerning the real-time recommendation and orchestration of post-disaster response plans. The implemented RES-Q prototype comprises an expert system and a workflow execution engine based on an ontological infrastructure for modeling the response actions for each type of disaster. The ontological model is designed using a multi-layer approach encapsulating the required knowledge streams and a semantic rule repository. During the execution of a post-disaster plan, the system reasons over the rules and composes the next steps of the corresponding response processes. The rule repository is able to infer new knowledge as each plan progresses, which can update the RES-Q ontology accordingly.

Keywords: disaster risk management, semantic web technologies, expert system, workflow engine

INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, disasters many of which are exacerbated by climate crisis exact an increasing toll on the well-being and safety of persons, communities, countries as a whole and economies. The Sendai Framework adopted at the Third UN World Conference on disaster risk reduction recognizes that managing risks and disasters is something that should be everyone's concern, identifying the need for new state of the art solutions that will leverage the engagement of societies and state institutions (Sendai/United Nations). The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development reaffirms the urgent need for effective disaster risk management (Agenda/United Nations).

Disaster risk management is the enforcement of policies, strategies and practices that aims to prevent or reduce the potential losses from hazards, assure prompt and appropriate assistance to victims of disaster, and achieve rapid and effective recovery (Twigg 2004). A conceptual model that's been utilized in traditional disaster management and civil protection involves the "Disaster Cycle", which includes three main phases: 1) Before the event, 2) Impact (during the event) and 3) After the event. The model acknowledges the variety of geological, meteorological, environmental, technological, socio-economic, and political threats to society and suggests that, in order to manage risks effectively, all these aspects should be taken into consideration (Corina Warfield).

To effectively support the recommendation and composition of the appropriate post-disaster plans in a process-oriented way, a software solution is needed so as to orchestrate the response and recovery processes efficiently (Serrano-Santoyo and Rojas-Mendizabal 2017). In this paper, we present the architecture of RES-Q, an ICT approach that combines a workflow management engine with an expert system and a semantic model in order

to meet the aforementioned challenges. The workflow tools provide the coordination models for disaster management in a formal way focusing on various stakeholder support. The expert system facilitates the dynamic adaptation of the post-disaster plans in order to enhance the flexibility of response schemes. During the execution of a response plan, the interaction of the semantic rules with the expert system provides valuable feedback to the system through the production of new facts and conclusions that can be used in further inference and ontology enhancement. Consequently, RES-Q semantic model constitutes a totally dynamic and self-evolving knowledge space.

The paper is structured as follows. The next section discusses our motivations and related work performed in the area of our interest. Section 3 overviews the RES-Q meta-model and the semantic infrastructure that will support the decision-making process. Subsequently, the paper presents the implemented RES-Q technical architecture alongside with a system walkthrough and detailed explanation. The final section concludes the paper and presents our future research orientations.

MOTIVATIONS AND RELATED WORK

Motivations

Alongside with the extensive study of the related work performed in the specific domain of our interest, the researchers conducted a set of interviews with professionals working in municipalities in Greece in order to define the requirements of the semantic infrastructure. The interviews were conducted in person, where semi-structured interview methods were used. All participants were smart city professionals whose experience ranged from 5 to 14 years and whose professional tasks ranged from being solely an IT specialist to being a manager and department head. Six professionals were engaged in the procedure and discussed the tasks and open issues concerning the participating entities during the dynamic composition of resiliency actions. The whole procedure was executed in six (6) interviews and lasted for nine (9) hours in total. Once the procedure concluded, a concrete overview was reached concerning the open issues and challenges emerging in the domain of our interest:

- *Formalization of response plans*: The formalization of response plans remains one of the major challenges for the area (Mohan and Mittal 2020). The lack of their formal representation in a computer perceptible form creates a major need, since their translation into structured knowledge and their integration within an IT system could facilitate the establishment of a mechanism for the recommendation of the next appropriate step and the orchestration of a response plan in an automatic and consistent way.
- *Maintenance*: Post-disaster response actions reflect on the available resources and infrastructure and on the multiple collaborative networks with various stakeholders and representatives from the emergency services, public and private companies, academic entities, media, citizens, and volunteer organizations. They must therefore be easily maintained so that the corresponding processes respond to the changes that may arise on the various involved stakeholders.
- *Semantic interoperability*: Smart city services, stakeholders and their knowledge bases often use different terms, types and values for data representation that do not support data interoperability. Without the provision of a uniform semantical basis, data interoperability cannot be achieved and that creates many difficulties during the integration and deployment of a response plan.
- *Knowledge discovery and evolution*: Current information feed to the response actions during execution mode is important, because the information collected could lead to major reconfigurations of the executed plans. Hence, the knowledge feedback is valuable, since it would be able to reconfigure the knowledge base together with the rules of the response actions.

Related work

Since Disaster management requires extensive and various information, especially during the post disaster phase, e.g., first responders, the location of people in danger, the safe evacuation routes, temporary shelters, etc., most of which have already made publicly available on the Web, Semantic Web has the ability to integrate heterogeneous data from diverse sources and allows different applications to share and reuse data between

them. The specific approaches rely on ontologies for representing conceptualized knowledge from the information. An ontology is a graph database that is composed of vocabularies and their relationships, e.g., in RDF or OWL. Applications may then query the ontology using query languages, e.g. SPARQL or OQL (Wang et al. 2020).

The study of (Chou et al. 2011) is the first to develop an ontology specifically for natural disaster management website elements, from an inventory of 6032 Web pages drawn from 100 disaster management Web sites in the United States (Wang et al. 2020). Selected semi-structured data representation approaches are used to organize the resulting ontology structure, which consists of 2094 Web elements. The ontology structure is further coded into a Web-based system, allowing easy online access. Overall, the specific approach covers all phases of natural disaster management and allows easy navigation of the ontology structure at different levels of detail. It can also serve as a foundation in the development of natural disaster management, assisting organizations, governments, and public authorities, who are involved in disaster management.

In the paper (Zhong et al. 2017) the authors proposed an ontology representation of domain knowledge of a meteorological disaster system descending from an adapted geospatial foundation ontology, designed to formally conceptualize the domain terms and establish relationships between those concepts. The multi-level ontology model was developed in a way that can provide semantic support during all the four faces of the Disaster Cycle, meaning before-, during-, after-event emergency management activities, such as risk assessment, resource preparedness, and emergency response where the formed concepts and their relationships can be incorporated into reasoning sentences of these decision processes.

The work of (Pandey and Bansal 2017) presents the use of semantic technologies to build an Emergency Management system called Safety Check. To that end, the authors analyzed the implementation of a knowledge intensive application that identifies individuals that may have been affected due to natural disasters or man-made disasters, such as earthquakes, floods, droughts, storms, cyclones, disease outbreak, etc., at any geographical location and provide safety instructions. The extraction of the necessary data was performed by various sources for emergency alerts, like earthquakes-weather alerts and contacts data, and afterwards they were integrated using a semantic data model and transformed into semantic data. Semantic reasoning was done through rules and queries. Another important aspect of the specific work is that there is a provision of collecting data, from social media websites like Facebook, Twitter LinkedIn, etc and even integrate with other emergency management organizations.

Furthermore, the main purpose of another research work was focused on the designing and implementation of a comprehensive geographic ontology, named GEO-MD, in the case of major disasters, based on pre and post-disaster satellite images (Bouyerbou et al. 2019). The goal of the specific ontology was to set a geographic vocabulary for major disasters context so as the formal representation of the domain knowledge to be useful for automatic satellite images processing, to assist the photo-interpreters in their data treatments and accelerate the relief operations in a crisis. The reuse of the ontology is also recommended for semantic content representation of satellite images, for change detection, as well as for performing queries related to the emergency needs.

The paper (Moßgraber et al. 2018) is focused on enhancing decision support and management services in extreme weather climate events, by providing support in all the phases of an emergency occurrence. To that end, the authors introduced the “beAWARE” project, which is an integrated solution to support forecasting, early warnings, transmission and routing of the emergency data, aggregated analysis of multimodal data and management of the coordination between the first responders and authorities. Even though the project relies on platforms, theories, and methodologies that are already used for disaster forecasting and management in previous works, its importance lies to the integration of a semantic perception in order to provide a more efficient way in handling the natural hazards based on the availability of the existing resources.

Paper (Chou et al. 2018) aims to present an ontology model with SWRL constructs to help the drill script generation process for earthquakes in Taiwan. At this point it should be highlighted that a disaster scenario can be expressed in a written form, called a drill script, which contains descriptions to mimic real-world events in accordance with a disaster’s progress in a given environment. However, not only the creation of a reasonable drill script is a time-consuming, error-prone, and costly task but also the level of a community’s disaster preparedness and readiness is also highly dependent on the quality of the drill scripts. Therefore, this research proposed an ontology model and system, called the Earthquake Drill Script generation and rendering System (EDSS), implemented using SWRL and Unity (a serious game platform) for generating drill scripts and for displaying a region with buildings affected by a simulated disaster.

Moreover, the main purpose of paper (Khantong and Ahmad 2020) is an effort to emphasize on the ontological concepts needed in the communication via speech act in the flood response management field, to reduce the large number of ontological concepts. As the authors state, even though the literature provides a variety of disaster response models, there are no ontologies that describe the disaster response domain from the point of view of communication between the involved organizations. Consequently, the proposed ontology was developed specifically for flood response management to provide a conceptual representation from the perspective of communication between the organizations involved. Technically speaking, the ontological concepts will be organized under upper ontological concepts, borrowed from the concept of interlocking institutional worlds, in which speech act theory is used as a foundation to present interactions among the organizations.

The research work produced by (Poslad et al. 2015) focused on deploying a Semantic IoT Early Warning System (EWS) used for environment disaster risk and effect management, to prevent loss of life and reduce the economic and material impact of disasters. In particular, the study examines geologic hazards, mainly on those on rapid onset, whose primary effect takes of the order of several tens of minutes up to days to primarily affect a region, rather than on slow onset hazards such as droughts whose primary effect can take months to years to occur. Additionally, different types of hazards differ in the types of IoT they use in terms of sensors, sensor mobility, and how these communicate, thus the authors used fixed environment sensors, excluding mobile sensors or remote sensors that have no direct contact with the natural environment, such as airborne sensors or satellites out in space.

In the paper (Gupta et al.) the authors proposed a framework to use both pre-event and post-event imagery for semantic change detection in conjunction with the OpenStreetMap (OSM) data to obtain an up-to-date road map of the affected areas. The proposed method contains 3 steps: 1) the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to segment the satellite images of the roads, 2) the conversion of the segmented images into a road network graph, 3) comparison of the pre and post disaster images in order to identify the impacted areas and possible missing road segments.

In the paper (Phengsuwan et al. 2020) a data integration and analytics system was proposed that enables an interaction between natural hazard Early Warning Systems (EWS) and electrical grid EWS to contribute to electrical grid network monitoring and support decision-making for electrical grid infrastructure management. For this purpose, and in order to identify the distribution poles in the electrical grid system that are vulnerable to landslide hazard and are likely to fail the Landslip Ontology was reused. As the authors state, the landslip Ontology was designed and developed to conceptualize the knowledge of landslide hazard and its warning signs. Overall, this system is an essential component that allows EWS to discover the relevant data sources and access rich information from the data sources.

OUR CONTRIBUTION

Our research led to the creation of the RES-Q software system, which enables the recommendation and orchestration of post-disaster response plans for each disaster type. Our contribution concerning the state-of-the-art in the disaster risk management domain could be presented in a three-fold structure:

1. *Dynamic composition of post-disaster response plans*: The innovation behind RES-Q approach is the fact that the predefined plan for each disaster is utilized only as a basis of the response scheme. RES-Q approach supports continuous reasoning over the semantically enhanced knowledge base and the established meta-models so as to dynamically compose each step of the response during execution. A key contribution towards the dynamic composition of the response plans is their proper computer modeling and encoding with harmonized and formalized terms across all stakeholders.
2. *RES-Q ontology*: The RES-Q ontology is able to nurture collaboration between the domains that are directly or indirectly linked with the disaster risk management area, bringing together stakeholders from diverse domains such as urban authorities, healthcare or seismology. To this regard, we introduce a novel ontological model for disaster risk management, which is designed based on a multi-layer approach. The RES-Q ontology has been developed as a core component of the RES-Q platform for integrating and semantically enriching disaster-related domain-specific concepts and metadata, which can be further utilized for the implementation of a repository of post-disaster response guidelines. The RES-Q ontology, however, can also be utilized as a standalone domain ontology.

3. *Establishment of post-disaster meta-models*: in any execution cycle, semantic meta-models are established by first executing a semantically annotated set of response guidelines for each disaster and, second, workflow execution to control the corresponding processes. RES-Q incorporates a rule repository created by utilizing Semantic Web Rule language (Horrocks et al. 2010) in order to extend the expressivity of the RES-Q ontological model. The rules are used in the inference process to reveal new facts from given ones and update the ontology accordingly, something not achievable using a relational database. The workflow environment covers the complete lifecycle of response plans (both design and execution mode) by offering a toolkit incorporating the BPMN process modeling notation.

THE RES-Q APPROACH

The RES-Q meta-model

The RES-Q orchestration methodology is based on the establishment of a post-disaster meta-model (Fig 1). An important component of the RES-Q approach is the perception of the proposed meta-model as a set of parent and child processes which constitute different levels of coordination models for disaster management supported by multiple stakeholders. The parent processes contain child processes and a set of decisions. Child processes typically comprise parallel execution workflows without decision-making leading to a new post-disaster status. Each plan to be executed will be a meta-model of a set of parent processes implemented using semantic reasoning and dictated by a rule-based expert system and child processes controlled in workflows. For example, in the scenario of a tsunami caused by an earthquake, the meta-model includes the "Tsunami start" parent process, which contains among others the "Evacuate people", "Protect the property" and "Transfer injuries to safe places" child processes.

Figure. 1 RES-Q meta-model

The meta-model allows the creation of parent and child sub-plans that can be stored in a repository and then composed by the RES-Q software environment during execution. In addition, the triggering of the rule-base during the reasoning process can be used to discover new knowledge, thus ensuring the perpetual enhancement and evolution of the RES-Q semantic model and knowledge base.

RES-Q ontology and rules

The cornerstone of the implemented integrated software environment is the RES-Q ontology, which is implemented by using a multi-layer approach so that it can represent both metadata and domain-specific concepts (Fig. 2). Terms in the domain-specific ontologies are ranked under the meta-contexts in the RES-Q upper model in such a way that the upper ontology classes represent supersets of all the classes in the domain ontologies. This modular approach allows various independent domain ontologies to be included under the top-level ontology to extend the semantic model. To develop the conceptual model, we followed the approach proposed in (Noy and McGuinness 2000).

Figure. 2 RES-Q multi-layer approach: Requirements are described by specific domain ontologies and top-level ontology

Fig. 3 provides an abstract view of the RES-Q upper ontology that presents the main conceptualization principles formalized by means of OWL-DL description logic language.

Figure. 3 RES-Q upper model

These classes represent the following knowledge:

Disaster: The concept refers to the disasters that take place and require response. It includes a classification of natural and manmade disasters. Disaster acts as a general concept by adopting the Emergency Disasters Database (EM-DAT), which provides a precise definition of concepts and furthermore a categorization of disturbance-related events.

Risk: This concept represents risks associated with disasters and facilitates policy making in prevention, preparedness, response, and reconstruction activities. Codenamed DOAM, the Description of a Model risk model is a domain ontology that aims to represent and categorize knowledge about risk management concepts using semantic web information technologies.

Agent as a person with a role: The concept represents the human individual. It contains the basic categories that describe a smart city agent who undertakes specific roles in the context of a disaster management response event. RES-Q uses Friend Of A Friend (FOAF) to describe people, relations, and respective roles. In order to identify an agent during a disaster, a data-type property associates an agent with a unique anonymous ID.

Process: The concept represents a process that is executed by a smart city agent in order to mitigate the impact of a disaster. During the design mode, a recovery process repository will be created in a centralized database that will allow an agent to retrieve the appropriate response plans to use during an emergency.

Infrastructure: The concept represents the set of fundamental facilities, resources and systems that can be used during the response to a disaster. RES-Q ontology utilizes SAREF4CITY, an extension of SAREF in order to create a common core of general concepts for smart city data oriented to material equipment, resources, IoT devices and infrastructure.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): The specific module that is modeled and interfaced as part of the RES-Q ontology is that of Key Performance Indicators in an arbitrary municipality by covering several quality assurance indicators. It supports a set of KPIs derived from domain experts' experience and perceptions.

Table 1 presents the vertical domain-specific ontologies and the state-of-the-art vocabularies that improve the prowess of the top-level ontology.

Table 1. Ontologies/classifications mapping to different dimensions of the RES-Q model

Knowledge steam	Ontologies/classifications
Agents	FOAF ¹
Risks	DOAM Risk Function Ontology ²
Infrastructure	SAREF ³ , s4city ⁴
Physical location	a-loc ⁵
Weather phenomena and exterior conditions	BIMERR ⁶
Roles	Smart DevOps role profiles ⁷
Disasters	EM-DAT ⁸
Seismology	SWEET ⁹

As the above table shows, the upper model acts as a semantic bridge supporting very broad semantic interoperability between various relevant domains, while at the same time it can be extended to cover more dimensions if necessary. In this way, it (a) facilitates knowledge reuse across various disaster risk management systems and applications, (b) enables distributed engineering of ontology modules over different locations and different areas of expertise, (c) supports effective management and browsing of modules, and (d) offers easier implementation, maintenance and update.

The semantic infrastructure incorporates an SWRL rule repository which models the knowledge involved in recommending the appropriate post-disaster interventions that should be conducted by smart city agents and all the other collaborating services and organizations. All rules are expressed in terms of OWL and include different concepts from the RES-Q ontology.

An indicative SWRL rule can be of the following form:

```
Disaster(?d1) ^ hasDisasterName(?d1, earthquake) ^ hasDetected(?d1, sea) ^
hasMagnitude(?d1, ?em) ^swrlb:greaterThan(?em, 7) ^
```

¹ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

² <https://www.openriskmanual.org/ns/doam/index-en.html>

³ <https://saref.etsi.org/core/v3.1.1/>

⁴ <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4city/v1.1.2/>

⁵ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/a-loc>

⁶ <https://bimerr.iot.linkeddata.es/def/weather/>

⁷ <https://smartdevops.eu/>

⁸ <http://www.emdat.be/Glossary>

⁹ https://esipfed.github.io/stc/sweet_lode/phenGeolSeismicity.html

```

Disaster(?d2) ^ hasDisasterName(?d2, tsunami) ^ causes(?d1, ?d2) ^
Agent(?a) ^ hasRole(?a, ChiefResilienceOfficer) ^
Process(?p) ^ executes(?a, ?p)
->
hasProcessName(?p, tsunamiStart)

```

Listing 1. Rule example

The rule describes the post-disaster response recommendation once an earthquake of Richter magnitude greater than 7 occurs and can in turn, cause a destructive tsunami. As elaborated in the ensuing discussion, an expert system fires the complete semantic ruleset in order to reason upon the stored knowledge and initialize the "TsunamiStart" workflow.

THE RES-Q PROTOTYPE

In this section we first present the technical architecture of the implemented prototype. Then, we describe its core components and the main functionalities via a system walkthrough.

Technical architecture

Fig.4 presents the technical architecture of the implemented web-based prototype, which comprises three (3) major software components:

Figure. 4 Technical architecture

RES-Q semantic model: As mentioned, the backbone of semantic infrastructure model is the RES-Q ontology designed using a multi-layer approach. The proposed approach promotes the production of extensive linked knowledge to be further used for decision-making dictated by the expert system component and for the dynamic composition of the appropriate post-disaster response processes controlled by the workflow engine component. The RES-Q semantic model is utilized for 1) the development of rules 2) the formalization of response plans and 3) the knowledge discovery and evolution through the dynamic generation of new facts by the rule engine. Protégé 5.5 tool was used, which is a popular and frequently used tool for ontology development, as well as checking the inconsistencies of classes and subclasses.

Expert system component: This technical component is responsible for the maintenance of the rule engine as well as the execution of the semantic rules. Initially, the semantic ruleset is implemented in SWRL to construct rule expressions in form of “Antecedent \Rightarrow Consequent” and perform reasoning tasks on the knowledge-base. During the design mode, the SWRL rules are transformed into Drools rules, and the result is stored in a file compatible with the rule engine. In this way, consistency in semantic terms is ensured since the required semantics originate directly from the ontology. The rule engine pinpoints and fires the appropriate ruleset to produce the result in JSON format. The JSON file has a custom structure and is utilized by the prototype for the selection of the appropriate workflows. Furthermore, the rule engine generates a feedback message that can update the ontology with previously unknown facts about the RES-Q knowledge base.

Workflow engine component: The Business layer of the RES-Q technical architecture contains also the workflow engine. The "Result manager" component processes the JSON result component and interacts with the workflow engine once the next process is needed. The core of the specific component is based on the Camunda workflow platform, which provides a web-based platform that enables users to handle workflow models. Additionally, the RES-Q design mode incorporates the Camunda Modeler tool to help users to create and edit workflow diagrams in BPMN format that work seamlessly with the Camunda engine. Conclusively, in our technical architecture, semantic web technologies are combined with Camunda APIs and the Drools expert system to support one unified web-based environment for modeling the post-disaster response plans as a combination of rules, processes and events.

Figure. 5 RES-Q design mode

RES-Q walkthrough

The software infrastructure that has been designed supports two distinct modes: the design mode and the execution mode. During the design mode, the respective actors maintain the accumulated knowledge inside the system and implement the appropriate rules and workflows, which model the domain knowledge for the disaster response composition. During the execution mode, the RES-Q software platform reasons upon the semantic rules to recommend all the required processes so as to facilitate the dynamic execution of the post-disaster response plan. The design mode is depicted in Fig. 5 and presents the implemented tsunami response plan in BPMN notation. The RES-Q execution mode is depicted in Fig. 6. As presented, the main interface has two main areas. The upper area that presents the proposed response steps for a specific disaster and the lower one that presents the status, actions and post-disaster process history in details. As depicted in Fig. 6, there are two (2) concurrent reasoning processes instantiated separately, the earthquake and the wildfires.

The lower part of the interface presents five different views of information:

Disaster information and stakeholders: the specific section holds details about the disaster alongside with useful information about the stakeholders engaged in the response plan.

Status: the specific section stores the status that the system passes through the post-disaster response plan execution.

Pending actions: this option contains the set of pending actions that need to be completed until the expert systems needs to reason over the new status for each disaster. The specific part of the response plan that can be executed without the decision of the implemented system represents a child process as defined by the meta-model.

Finished actions: the specific option stores the complete list of the already finished actions, together with the associated meta-data (dates, actors etc.).

Disaster report history: each disaster is accompanied by a list of reports gathered by the previous reasoning sessions. As the execution of a scenario progresses, more information is collected by the RES-Q system.

The current research work has been developed within the RES-Q Living Lab (RESCUE Living lab) under the framework of the INVEST4EXCELLENCE program (INVEST, n. d.). We are now in close cooperation with various stakeholders facilitating quadruple helix partnerships of research, education, companies from the IT sector and local authorities from region of Thessaly in Greece aiming at open end-user-oriented innovation. We have modeled three (3) experimental post-disaster response plans, implemented the corresponding rules and workflows and we are in the process of scaling up to pilot stage.

#	Disaster	Response
4	Earthquake	EarthquakeStart -> EarthquakeEnd -> TsunamiStart
5	Wildfires	WildfiresStart -> WaterSupplyNetworkFixStart

Wildfires

[Disaster information and Stakeholders](#)
[Status](#)
[Pending actions](#)
[Finished actions](#)
[Report history](#)

Figure. 6 RES-Q execution mode

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we present the RES-Q approach, an ICT software solution for providing composition of self-evolving post-disaster response processes. More specifically, this research work proposes the integration of semantic web technologies with workflow and rule engine for the recommendation and orchestration of the corresponding processes. The modeling of response plans is performed by the establishment of a multi-layer semantic infrastructure the core of which is a top-level ontology accompanied with various independent domain-specific ontologies. In this way, it facilitates the capture of domain knowledge at different levels of granularity in order to leverage semantic interoperability between various agents and heterogeneous domains. With the use of RES-Q semantic model and rules, it is possible to deduce new facts, thus discovering new chunks of knowledge, which are stored inside RES-Q ontology. Moreover, through continuous reasoning, the execution of disaster risk management plans is constantly adapted since it is based on a holistic and self-evolving knowledge base. The current research work has been developed with a Living Lab approach in coherence with the INVEST4EXCELLENCE European project. Under the RES-Q pilot, the areas of the Living

Lab - as micro versions of larger territories - can be seen as appropriate sites for validating and spreading new concepts, processes and technologies, serving as showcases at macro level. Thus, scalability and replicability to other regions is strongly embedded in the RES-Q project.

Our future work will be devoted to ontology enhancement and expansion. The enhancement will focus on smart city infrastructure issues and health-related knowledge representation. Our intention is to implement complex rules that combine concepts and instances from various domain ontologies. In addition, we plan to concentrate on providing role-based access control and different views of the response plan for different user roles. This feature will allow different stakeholders to work with content and portions of the plan depending on the role they have.

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